

The Mediating Role of Auditing in Shared Value Optimization through Big Data Analytics:
A Conceptual Review

Salem Udoh¹ and Khaled Mohamed Tomas Bata University, Zlin, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

The essence of big data and big data analytics as technological breakthroughs is to create and share value among stakeholders. Numerous studies focus on the impact of big data analytics upon firm's performance, big data analytics and auditing and big data with created shared value. There is very little if any study on the mediating role of auditing in the relationship between big data analytics and shared value optimization. As a methodology, we used 'Publish or Perish' which is an academic "search engine" to search all the articles on the big data analytics and firm performance; big data analytics and auditing; big data analytics and shared value optimization topics available on Google Scholar without time limit. Our initial search found 1000 studies as articles, books and other publications. Based on our criteria, we included only 32 articles focusing on big data analytics and auditing (n=18); big data analytics and created shared value (n=14); and, without big data analytics and firm performance (n=18) already substantially covered in extant literature. The main finding is that there is no study to our knowledge and study's limitation on the mediating role of auditing in the tripartite relationship following our conceptual model based on optimization theory given the importance of information integrity for stakeholders.

KEYWORDS: big data analytics, firm performance, created shared value optimization, auditing

¹ Corresponding author. E-mail address: udoh@utb.cz